

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017454

reSEARCH-EU

Report on the Consolidation of the SEA-EU Open Research Data Policies

Milestone M15

(due to M36, Dec 2023)

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1. Deliverable identification

Deliverable No. and Title	M15. Report on the Consolidation of the SEA-EU Open Research Data Policies
Leader	Mr. Kevin J. Ellul
Related task(s)	Tasks 5.1 and 5.2
Authors	reSEArch-EU Open Research Data Officers
Dissemination level	Public
Due submission date	30/11/2023
Submission	15/11/2023
Project number	101017454
Start date of project	01/01/2021
Duration	36 months
<p>This a report on progress with regard to the consolidation of the Open Research Data policies in the respective universities of the SEA-EU Alliance. It outlines how the SEA-EU RDM Policy framework is being adopted at each University.</p>	

2. Versions and contributions history

1. Version	Date	Modified by	Reason
First draft of the report	19 th October 2023	Open Science Data Officers and Technical Managers	Reviewing by individual partners
Second draft of the report	12 th November 2023	Godfrey Baldacchino	Internal review
Final draft	28 th October 2023	Prepared by Kevin Ellul and Josianne Vella	Final version
Final version	12 th November 2023	Godfrey Baldacchino	Internal review
Final version	17 th November 2023	Kevin Ellul, Josianne Vella, Godfrey Baldacchino and Aldo Drago	Completion and submission

1. Introduction

This report presents an analysis of responses obtained from a questionnaire distributed amongst the Open Research Data Officers (ORDOs) of the six SEA-EU partner universities involved in reSEARCH-EU. The scope of this questionnaire was to gather feedback on how the SEA-EU Research Data Management Policy Framework is being adopted within the respective SEA-EU partner universities.

2. The questionnaire

The questionnaire consisted of five open-ended questions as follows:

1. How is the SEA-EU Research Data Management (RDM) Policy Framework supporting your university with the implementation of its RDM principles and practices?
2. What changes have been implemented at your institution after the adoption of the SEA-EU Research Data Management Policy Framework? Have there been any advances in terms of policies, infrastructures and/or training initiatives?

3. What changes or initiatives are you planning to implement within your university to support your researchers with the implementation of RDM practices and principles?
4. What would you recommend to ensure the best possible harmonisation of the SEA-EU Research Data Management Policy Framework with your own university's RDM policies?
5. What tools are being used by your university to support RDM (Data Management Plans, anonymization software, etc.)?

Responses were received by the ORDOs of all six SEA-EU partner universities involved in reSEARCH-EU, being:

- University of Cadiz (UCA), Spain
- University of Western Brittany (UBO), France
- Kiel University (CAU), Germany
- University of Gdańsk (UG), Poland
- University of Split (UNIST), Croatia
- University of Malta (UM), Malta

3. Key Themes

The following key themes emerged from the SEA-EU Research Data Management (RDM) Policy Framework questionnaire responses:

- Policy development
- Training, awareness and dissemination of information
- Tools
- Evaluation
- Harmonisation
- Innovation

3.1 Policy Development

The SEA-EU RDM Policy Framework has provided a foundation for the compilation of a Research Data Management (RDM) policy at the University of Malta (UM) and the University of Gdansk (UG), both of whom lacked such policies. At the University of Split (UNIST), the SEA-EU Policy Framework has strengthened existing practices. Additionally, at Kiel University (CAU), the Policy framework was used to review and revise the University's existing institutional RDM guidelines incorporating the FAIR Data Principles.

3.2 Training, awareness and dissemination of information

All six SEA-EU partner universities offer training workshops on RDM, as well as other support mechanisms. For example, UM has developed a web page with detailed guidance on RDM, compiled a users' guide on how to upload data on the data repository and delivers lectures to doctoral students on open research data practices and how to effectively make the best use of the data repository. UNIST offers training and support in the Croatian language, including an RDM handbook, webinars and online courses. UG is developing a training proposal for students and staff. Moreover, UG is preparing guidelines for creating a data management plan (DMP). CAU plans to expand its existing training services to support national and international RDM initiatives. UBO offers workshops on data management aimed at researchers and PhD students, and plans to communicate the RDM toolkit to raise awareness and encourage its usage. UCA has created guidelines for researchers on open access and data management, and is planning to launch training sessions to enhance researchers' knowledge pertaining to RDM.

3.3 Tools

All six SEA-EU partner universities offer a data repository, as well as other tools and resources to support RDM. These include guidelines and information on their websites (UM, UNIST, UCA), a survey creator (UNIST), a DMP template/creator (UNIST, UG, CAU, UBO), data storage facilities (UNIST, CAU, UBO), research data anonymisation tool (UNIST), digitisation service (CAU), a Collaborative Development Environment (CAU), and a decisional tool to support researchers with legal aspects (UBO).

3.4 Evaluation

UBO plans to collect information on researchers' data management practices through a survey at the end of 2023 to identify resources used by researchers and areas for improvement.

3.5 Harmonisation

To help with the harmonisation of the six SEA-EU partner universities' RDM policies with the SEA-EU RDM Policy Framework, the following recommendations were made:

- sharing of best practices between SEA-EU partners
- staff networking
- training sessions with partner universities.

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3.6 Innovation

An educational game, called DMPoly, is being developed by UG as part of its efforts to raise awareness and educate researchers about the various facets of data management.

4. Conclusion

The SEA-EU Research Data Management Policy Framework has provided a solid foundation for the creation of RDM policies at the six SEA-EU partner universities engaged in reSEArch-EU, while strengthening existing practices within other institutions. All SEA-EU partner universities offer training, awareness raising initiatives, and dissemination of information, tools, and resources to support researchers in implementing RDM practices and principles. Harmonisation of the six SEA-EU partner universities' RDM policies with the SEA-EU Policy Framework can be achieved through the sharing of best practices, staff networking, and training sessions. A list of RDM tools and resources made available to researchers of the six SEA-EU partner universities is provided via the SEA-EU RDM Toolkit.